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How different are engineering design projects? An analysis of middle school lessons and units

S Purzer

Associate Professor
Purdue University
West Lafayette, Indiana, USA
E-mail: purzer@purdue.edu

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ABSTRACT

Engineering education has gained momentum in K-12 education in recent years. However, available curricula and teaching materials take a variety of approaches, guided by limited research identifying or comparing these approaches. Using content analysis, I analysed, classroom-tested and published engineering lessons used in middle school grades (ages 13-15). The evaluation resulted in five types of implementation: design-build-test projects, experimentation tasks that highlight engineering science principles, contextualised problem solving through integrated STEM units, innovation projects where students identify a need and pursue their own projects, and optimization tasks with a focus on improving a suboptimal system. These implementation methods differ based on their goals, what part of the design process they engage, and the activities they emphasize. The variations in teaching models suggest differences need to be well-understood by educators and curriculum designers. Future research is necessary examining differences in student learning outcomes associated with the differences in the implementation models.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 The need for the study

In recent years there has been an increased interest in teaching engineering design in K-12 school as part of the STEM education movement that is gaining momentum globally. It is important that the university professors in engineering programs are aware of these developments, as these changes in K-12 education are likely create changes at the university level including who decides to pursue engineering and how those who pursue engineering perceive engineering.

In Europe, STEM education projects are promoted through programs such as ERASMUS+ and SCIENTIX. In the United States, the Next Generation Science Standards, further urges for the integration of science and engineering while promoting three dimensional learning that emphasize disciplinary core ideas, science and engineering practices, and cross-cutting concepts [1]. In alignment with these developments that emphasize the importance of teaching engineering in K-12 education, the National Assessment of Education progress (NAEP) in the US added technology and engineering literacy to its suite of assessments in 2014. Similarly, in 2015, PISA added a new test on collaborative problem solving to the group of its tests in reading, science, and mathematics literacy.

As these efforts evolve, it is important that K-12 educators have a framework for designing curriculum in alignment with the nature of engineering, and that teachers have the tools to be able to judge quality depending on the learning objectives they want to cover in their lessons.

1.2 Review of the literature

Teaching engineering in the K-12 classrooms is a fairly new practice. Although there is interest and necessity to teach engineering, teachers, curriculum developers, and even teacher educators are often not familiar with the discipline of engineering and the pedagogical methods associated with teaching engineering design. As a result there are a variety of ways engineering is taught in schools. However, there is little research comparing differences in these approaches (e.g., [2,3]). Svihla and colleagues compared kit-based projects and re-design projects, though their study was at the college level. Goldstein and colleagues compared a small-scale design project with a large-scale interdisciplinary project. They found that student learning in engineering science concepts were higher in the large-scale project while students who worked on the small-scale project developed a more robust understanding of trade-off decisions in design.

1.3 Purpose

While more studies on the status, role, and impact of engineering education in elementary and secondary school are necessary, as a first step we need to identify variations in implementation methods. Initially the analysis started with the goal of evaluating lesson plans for authenticity and to what extent they reflect epistemic

practices in engineering. However, the variations observed did not allow the use as scoring protocol that can be applied to evaluate each variation. Hence, the approach was revised to describe variation. To address the need to identify variation, this study involved the analysis of classroom-tested, peer-reviewed and published descriptions of units and curricula with a focus on engineering. The content of these articles is reviewed to identify variations in teaching engineering in K-12 education.

2 RESEARCH METHODS

2.1 Sample

The detailed descriptions of all lesson plans and units published in the decade (between 2007 and 2018) in the Science Scope magazine of the National Association for Science Teaching made up the data pool. The articles published in the Science Scope are peer-reviewed and have previously been used in the classroom (see <http://www.nsta.org/middleschool>). They are also authored by classroom teachers, university faculty, or both. A total of 71 articles mentioned engineering in the text. These articles are then reviewed carefully to identify those that describe a lesson or a unit with a focus on engineering. The resulting data set included 39, which were used for in-depth analysis.

2.2 Data Analysis

A thematic analysis method [4] is used to identify themes explaining types of lesson. First the researcher read all 39 articles in full. This process was accompanied with an open coding process. Multiple interactions of coding and re-reading led to the development of themes.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Themes

The analysis resulted in five different ways engineering is represented in middle school classes. These themes are determined based on their focus on specific components of the design process and include:

1. *Design-build-test* projects
2. *Experimentation* tasks that highlight engineering science principles
3. *Conceptualized problem solving* through integrated STEM units
4. *Innovation* projects where students identify a need and pursue own projects
5. *Optimization* tasks with a focus on improving a suboptimal system

The majority of the articles described lessons that used a design-build-test approach followed by eleven articles that had a focus on experimentation and engineering sciences (see Figure 1). In the **design-build-test** approach the students had some flexibility in determining their design solutions within the constraints of the materials that were provided. There was much variation in the authorship of these articles. Some were written by school teachers while others were authored by teachers and STEM

education faculty. In the **experimentation** category, students followed a fairly scripted procedure to build a testable prototype and were more engaged in testing the prototype in a controlled setting. These were typically authored by engineering faculty and graduate students.

The third category was **contextualized problem solving**. These included real projects that are implemented with an interdisciplinary team of teachers as well as simulated projects with a fictional client. In either case, however, students spent a considerable amount of time understanding the problems and the context before generating solutions.

Fig. 2. The frequency of each type of engineering project or task

The fourth category was **innovation**. In these projects, students identified a need and determined their own projects to pursue within a broad topic are such as biomedical engineering. Teachers guided multiple variations of problems that the students pursued. In addition, experts (university professors) visited classrooms and presented their research and engaged students in small tasks associated with the topic. Hence, collaboration between the school and the university was vital.

The final category included **optimization** with a focus on re-design, rather than a new design. Students started with an existing solution that was suboptimal. They observed its problems and identified solutions to optimize its performance.

An example for each category is presented in Table 1.

3.2 Themes and the Stages of the Design process

Further analysis revealed that the five themes identified were also associated with specific stages of the design process (see Figure 2). For example, optimization tasks involved students in testing and re-design cycles as students started with a suboptimal solution. On the other hand, innovation category required students to define a need and engage a full design-process cycle.

Fig. 2. Types of engineering projects and tasks represented in lessons

Table 1. Engineering task examples

Type	Articles in the category	Example Task
Design-build-test	Bartus, 2017; Berge, 2014; Crismond, 2013; Feille, 2017; German, 2017; Goldberg, 2013; Kennedy, 2014; Kern, 2015; Loterero-Perdue, 2013; Love, 2015; Meyer, 2014; Miranda, 2013; Moore, 2014; Thiam, 2017; Williamgham, 2016	Students are introduced to oceanography and tasked to design a self-sustaining ocean platform that can withstand the movement of water and sediments and with minimal impact on the ocean life [5].
Experimentation (build + test)	Turgeon, 2014; Vassilier, 2013; Ballyns, 2011; Chen, 2014; Garafolo, 2017; Hoffmann, 2013; Ing, 2013; Khaldi, 2016; King, 2014; Nguyen, 2014; Sandone, 2017*	In a lesson on tissue engineering, students followed a protocol to build columns made from alginate. They tested their specimens using compression tests. Their goal was to produce the strongest material using alginate gel [6].
Contextualized problem-solving	Ewalt, 2015**; Goldstein, 2017**; Karahan, 2014; Wang, 2017; Abbott, 2016; Rupp, 2014;	In a STEM curriculum composed of six lessons, the students are first introduced to an issue published in a local newspaper, describing how a farmer accidentally destroyed a pelican colony. After estimating the number of nests in pelican colonies (math) and ecology concepts and food webs (science) students design pelican nests that can be safely moved while maintaining the temperature of the pelican eggs [7].

Innovation	Helfer, 2016; Nicholas, 2015; Zwart, 2013;	Students are asked to identify gaps in the existing technology in neuromuscular control and prosthetics. They developed prosthetic design solutions to meet a specific purpose such as drawing [8].
Optimization (test+ re-design)	Dasgupta, 2017; Lancaster, 2015	Students are provided with a plumbing system which is not optimally designed. Students test the system to evaluate its problem and re-design an optimize system [9].

4 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This study examined variations in how engineering is implemented in middle school classrooms. The analysis resulted in five categories, where each had a different type of emphasis on an aspect of engineering (e.g., engineering science vs engineering design). This study is a critical contribution to the body of literature as these categories can be used: 1) to guide the development of curricula associated with a given type of implementation, 2) support research comparing different approaches used to teaching engineering concepts and practices in K-12 education.

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